

AI Going Rogue?

An integrative academic review of the tacit assumptions underlying existential AI-risks.

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Abstract

This paper presents an integrative narrative review of the tacit background assumptions underlying AI existential risk (X-risks) futures. Once confined to science fiction, concerns about AI X-risks now shape debates at the crossroads of the tech world, NGOs, politics and (social) media. Despite growing attention, the plausibility of AI surpassing human controllability remains highly contested. Examining 81 peer-reviewed papers from Scopus and Web of Science, we find a fragmented discourse characterized by bold yet often unsubstantiated claims, including accelerationist growth models and speculative calculations of catastrophic tipping points. Anthropomorphic and speculative AI conceptualizations prevail, while interdisciplinary perspectives that consider issues of infrastructure, social agency, Big Tech power position and politics remain scarce. Delineating how these speculative tendencies are detrimental to the current regulatory need to tackle AI harms, we deduce an AI X-risk plausibility list and advocate for a shift in attention from the maximum possible negative consequences to the structural and socio-technical characteristics of how AI is embedded - which are the prerequisites for any AI futures to emerge.

Keywords

artificial intelligence, existential risk, catastrophic risk, epistemic uncertainty, controllability, integrative review

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Introduction

As artificial intelligence (AI) and its capabilities continues to advance, a once-niche debate confined to expert circles and science fiction novels is now at the forefront of public discourse: the risk of AI surpassing human controllability and causing catastrophic consequences. Existential risk (X-risk) positions discuss AI as a potentially autonomous agent. They raise concerns about power-seeking intelligence(s) that could seize control over critical infrastructure – or even over humanity as an entirety.

While scenarios of a sudden hostile takeover, societal collapse and apocalyptic destruction may sound like the plot of science-fiction blockbusters, they are increasingly shaping real-world policy discussions. In 2023, amid the global frenzy surrounding ChatGPT, the American Future of Life Institute (FLI) called for an immediate six-months pause to the training of AI systems, warning of the potential dangers of creating “nonhuman minds that might eventually outnumber, outsmart, obsolete and replace us”, and questioning whether we should “risk loss of control of our civilization“ [36]. This appeal for a moratorium on AI development was soon accompanied by a statement from the San Francisco based Center for AI Safety (CAIS), which gathered signatures from AI experts, the broader scientific audience, and public figures. Their statement urged global leaders to recognize AI-related extinction risks – and their mitigation – as priorities on par with other societal-scale threats such as pandemics and nuclear war [24].

The narrative of catastrophic AI is already influencing power dynamics, materializing in policy decisions and creating political lock-in effects. In September 2023, European Union Commission President Ursula von der Leyen literally echoed the warning by CAIS about the “risk of extinction from AI” in her speech to the EU parliament [100]. A year later, in October 2024, computer scientist and influential X-risk and AI safety spokesperson Yoshua Bengio was appointed to chair one of the European Commission’s Code of Practice working groups on general purpose AI [104]. In the United States, the X-risk narrative has also begun to shape policy. The Californian bill SB1047⁴, co-drafted by CAIS, proposed the creation of an oversight board, mandatory safety testing for AI models, and legal liability for Big Tech companies. However, the bill, which was regarded as a prototype for national legislation, was framed in a distinctly alarmist X-risk narrative, holding companies responsible for “mitigat[ing] the risk of catastrophic harms from AI models so advanced that they are not yet known to exist” [13, p. 1]. Critics argue that such legislative proposals steered and continue to steer the American policy debate toward speculative future threats rather than addressing the tangible, immediate challenges posed by AI and its societal integration [1, 67]. Perhaps the most striking example of X-risk thinking intersecting with political power is the alliance between tech billionaire and FLI external advisor Elon Musk – who already in 2014 called AI “our biggest existential threat” and that “humanity risks ‘summoning a demon’” [38] – and US president Donald Trump. Or the close contact between venture capitalist Peter Thiel and tech-accelerationist Marc Andreessen with Vice president JD Vance. These alliances have shifted the AI X-risk agenda into the center of national policy making.

Amidst the influence of the X-risk discourse on politics and regulation, public controversies about AI scenarios beyond human controllability show a divided and polarized picture, reacting to the particularly emotional and drastic frame of X-risks. After all, doomsday scenarios imply drastic opportunity costs and a closing window of action to mitigate the absolute worst-case effects for humanity. Consequently, they are highly performative and resemble the characteristics of hypes [12], catching substantial media attention. Nordmann [73] refers to these ‘if and then’ scenarios as evocative ‘speculative ethics’, which can create forceful and unchecked futures by means of a “radical foreshortening of the conditional” [73, p. 32]. Hence, for some figures, the risks of AI are on par with other catastrophic risks such as the global nuclear threat, and thus urgently call for related policy intervention. Among these proponents are notable and well-acclaimed scientists, which grants this trajectory considerable legitimacy and media attention⁵. Conversely, critics and skeptics contend that the discussion surrounding the

⁴ Turned down by Democrat governor Newsom in August, 2024.

⁵ Notable signers of the before mentioned letters are well established scientists, as well as controversial entrepreneurs: Geoffrey Hinton, Yoshua Bengio, Nick Bostrom, Yuval Noah Hariri, Sam Altman, or Elon Musk.

potential loss of AI controllability allocates important intellectual, regulatory and material resources that could be better used elsewhere, pointing to the risks and associated socio-structural issues with AI in the here and now. Examples include the monopolisation of Big Tech power, societal dependencies on privately held infrastructure, or the policing of vulnerable groups supported by AI-based means (see, e.g., [55, 69, 85, 102]). These authors discuss the mere assumption of the possibility of AI beyond human controllability as scientifically unfounded, or even as a discourse-political maneuver on the part of proponents of human enhancement, tech-accelerationism and longtermist thinking [17, 37]. Further, explicit normative critiques contest the Western mechanistic and reductionist framing of intelligence as posited by tech-accelerationist perspectives, delineating these views as not doing justice to the variety of intelligence conceptions stemming from other epistemic communities [12].

Scientific scholarship has started to investigate and structure the scattered AI X-risk discourse. There are comprehensive reviews of the academic literature describing scenarios of AI beyond human controllability and issues of AI safety, ranging from a sudden takeover by power-seeking AI, to AI runaway dynamics along a misalignment with human values [46-47, 65-66, 98]. Gebru and Torres [37] also offer a normative mapping of the different ideological origins of the X-risk discourse, outlining what they refer to as the TESCREAL bundle (transhumanism, extropianism, singularitarianism, cosmism, rationalism, effective altruism, and longtermism) along their respective historical roots. However, while the existing literature outlines various scenarios of AI beyond controllability, maps AI safety issues, and clusters their proponents according to their underlying ideologies, it offers little reflection on the very *preconditions* of these futures.

Therefore, this paper addresses the following question: What conceptual enablers, probability horizons and tacit assumptions serve as building blocks in the construction of these futures? In essence, no matter the evocative frame and normative contestations, scientific research falls short to scrutinize the underlying *plausibility* of the futures deployed. The perspective on plausibility matters greatly because it (de-)legitimizes political attention to certain futures and their adjunct risks. For regulators, the question of whether X-risks are what Brock [20] calls “wishful worries”, i.e., “problems that it would be nice to have, as opposed to the actual agonies of the present”, or plausible (even if distant) futures that they need to consider, is crucial.

As shown above, many non-scientific actors contribute towards the public debate on AI X-risks. Sotala & Yampolskiy [88] also observe in their review of the literature on AI and X-risks, that this scattered yet polarized debate is dominated by non-peer-reviewed publications, such as blogs, books and commentaries⁶. A further issue are very influential Silicon Valley figures like Elon Musk, Peter Thiel, Marc Andreessen and Sam Altman, or controversial academics like Nick Bostrom and Toby Ord. These proponents stem from the Longtermist movement and inject the scientific discourse with sensationalist and alarmist claims about AI capabilities, granting them attention, political power, and the attraction of venture capital [94-95]. This strategic opportunism is staged in (social-) media and influences public opinion and sentiments around AI, which further complicates a critical and structured analysis of the plausibility of AI X-risks. We take these circumstances as a further motivation to approach the construction of plausibility of AI X-risks with scientific scrutiny.

To do justice to this task, we turn to the academic debate to conduct an integrative narrative literature review [28, 92] of explicitly peer reviewed academic publications on AI X-risk scenarios. We hypothesize that the stringent standards for indexing in Scopus and Web of Science ensure that the included journals and articles are held to rigorous scrutiny, also concerning their quality of argumentation. This renders them well-suited for a critical, plausibility-focused review of AI X-risks futures. The only work we identified that approaches the discourse in a comparable manner – focusing on the “assumptions of AGI” – is Blili-Hamelin et al. [17]. However, their contribution primarily explores the different conceptions of intelligence within the Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) discourse. Our search string, on the other hand, did not include such a constrained focus and targeted the entire discourse surrounding AI (without G) potentially acting beyond human controllability. While the work by

⁶ Even though there is a scientific community assembling around the conferences and Journal of the Artificial General Intelligence Society.

Blili-Hamelin et al. [17] is rather conceptual – zooming-in only on a small-set of literature – it provides helpful orientation points we will refer to during our analysis of the corpus.

We deduced 81 contributions listed in Scopus and Web of Science Core (WOS) along the following guiding questions:

1. How is AI defined and related to existential risk, and how is risk understood?
2. How are time, probability and plausibility horizons conceptualised concerning the risks of an out-of-control AI?
3. Which background conditions (material, institutional, economic) as well as societal circumstances are discussed in the futures towards out-of-control AI?

The paper is structured as follows. First, the conceptual and methodological approach is presented, tackling the challenge of how to assess a speculative realm of a far-fetched future and its associated scientific discourse. Then, the integrative analysis addresses the three questions above, deconstructing the prevalent conceptual background conditions and tacitly deployed narratives. The concluding discussion proposes an AI X-risk plausibility list (Table 1), and advocates for a discursive shift in attention from the maximum possible negative consequences of AI to the characteristics of AI that are assumed to be conditions for these consequences in the here and now.

Methods of assessing the speculative: a hermeneutical approach to unravelling tacit assumptions

This review assesses and systematises a trope of knowledge that requires distinct conceptual and methodological lenses: How to assess something that is so speculative, yet would have the most detrimental consequences if it were to occur? While the former diminishes the urgency from an epistemological and political point of view, the latter highlights the high stakes involved. Existential risks differ fundamentally from other types of risks. In general, risks are always associated with uncertainty and are usually quantified according to the formula “amount of loss times probability of occurrence” to render them tangible and allow for a certain degree of comparability [78]. However, the speculative character of ‘existential’ risks, coupled with their implied ‘all-humans-affecting’ scope, makes their assessment a particularly challenging scientific undertaking.

With regard to uncertain future technology and innovation paths, Technology Assessment (TA), Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Science and Technology Studies (STS), have reacted with future directed heuristics. Speculative trajectories can be deconstructed and substantiated, among others, through hermeneutical vision assessment [35, 43], approaches oriented at anticipations and expectations [4, 56], or forecasting methods [61-62]. Scrutinizing speculative futures and their plausibility involves analysing hypotheses that lack the crucial epistemological quality of verifiability or falsifiability. The discourse revolving around AI X-risks is characterised by such a high degree of uncertainty that their “conus of possible futures” cannot be reduced argumentatively to a manageable number of assessable scenarios [45, p. 68], thus allowing for neither a prognostic nor a scenario-based literacy. Instead, the discourse at hand reflects a plurality of tropes and meanings, with overlaps of scientific and non-scientific views, and standpoints that mediate between fact and fiction. All in all, the AI X-risk discourse represents speculative futures that cannot be proven or disproven, but only be judged as (in)plausible. This is why, in our analysis, we place particular emphasis on the *background(ed) assumptions* leveraged to lend plausibility to the respective AI future in question. This analysis establishes not only the foundation for a scientific critique of the prevalent positions, but also an identification of the “deficiencies, omissions, inaccuracies, and other problematic aspects” [92, p. 362] found in the prognostics of the AI X-risk discourse. Hence, we will not only focus on what is said, but also on what is ignored and muted because it could complicate the projection of AI futures to come. As will be shown in the analysis below, this notion of overshadowing – understood as strategic ignorance [64] – creeps into the AI X-risk futures through the negation of social and scientific complexity, or the sidelining of counter-arguments from different scientific disciplines.

Looking at the consequences sketched, the AI futures under consideration work with a certain rhetorical escalation, employing maximum stakes along the lines of ‘existential’, ‘going rogue’, ‘gaining the upper hand’ and ‘apocalyptic’ framings. As many positions in the corpus emphasise the utmost urgency in dealing with existential risks, we also examine the theatrical techniques [39] and the “dramaturgical regime” [74] of the articles

in question – implying that that their “performative imaginations are enacted” with figurative language and performative tweaks that can be deconstructed [74, p. 259]. This motivates us to pay particular attention to the rhetorical devices utilised, such as metaphors, analogies and exaggerations, which underscore narratives of grandeur, predictive precision, or threat (as practised in hermeneutic approaches; e.g. in vision assessment [35], RRI [44] or in hype studies [12]).

This integrative narrative literature review is limited to original articles listed in Scopus and WOS. The search in both databases was conducted on 27 September 2024, using the following Boolean search terms developed in accordance with our research interest: ‘(ALL=((‘existential risk*‘ OR “catastrophic* risk*” OR “human extinction”)) AND (‘artificial intelligence‘ OR ai))) OR ALL=(‘uncontroll* artificial intelligence‘ OR “uncontroll* ai”) and “(ALL=(rogue artificial intelligence OR ”rogue ai’))’. The following inclusion criteria were applied in the selection of articles for review: The publication primarily focuses on existential risk, particularly the role of artificial intelligence, and is written in English. These criteria were then used to evaluate the titles and abstracts of all retrieved articles. Articles that did not meet the eligibility criteria were omitted from the review, e.g. articles that only briefly mention X-risks without discussing them further. A total of 233 contributions were found (WOS 74, Scopus 159). 45 duplicates were removed. The abstracts (if available) of the remaining 188 articles were reviewed for relevance and then discussed by the author team. 110 articles remained for qualitative assessment along the questions delineated above. Each article in the final sample was read and reviewed by (at least) two of the three reviewers, based on a coding sheet informed by the research interest sketched out above. During this qualitative analysis, a further 29 articles were eliminated from the corpus given that they fall short in meeting the specified criteria.

Integrative narrative analysis

1) How to define AI? From performative anthropomorphisation and complexity games to sentient AI

As a departure point in the X-risk discourse we investigate how the literature defines AI and relates it to existential risk (RQ 1). The comparison with human capabilities constitutes a focal anchor for many authors seeking to define AI, next to metaphysical and contested AI conceptualization as discussed below.

Turing’s AI: setting the ground for the AI vs. human competition

The Turing test remains a popular point of reference (e.g., [1-2, 16, 52]). The test, originally termed ‘imitation game’ by Alan Turing, characterizes the founding momentum of modern AI research, placing human-machine comparison at the very centre of the debate. Since Turing, this comparison is invoked to track AI capabilities, with humans representing a competing rival. This competitive framing suggests a recurrent anthropomorphisation as a backdrop and an AI potentially out of control as one that perspectively outruns the human. To evaluate the performance it is common practice in computer science to propose challenges or quests in which the players compete in a human vs. machine format. Historically, these challenges have been modelled in the form of complexity games, involving *breakthroughs* in the field of chess (‘Deep Blue’), ‘Jeopardy!’ and ‘GO’ (‘Aleph Alpha’). To measure the performance in complexity games there is a prevailing tendency in the literature corpus to invoke benchmarks, with the objective of providing a tangible illustration of AI’s capabilities [29]. Doing so, authors subtly imply that the resolution of humanity’s challenges is tantamount to a quest for mastering complexity. The apparently hardest complexity challenge that contemporary AI, in the form of Large Language Models (LLM), is facing is aptly named ‘Humanity’s Last Exam’ [75] – before even titled ‘Humanity’s Last Stand’ [80]. This framing rhetorically implies a performative, looming threat for humanity, and drastic consequences if AI ‘passes the exam’, ultimately testifying that AI can defeat and conquer the human.

Benchmarks used as a point of reference for AI capabilities have been criticized for being narrow and reductionist, essentially committing an inductive fallacy. Raji et al. [78] and Eriksson et al. [33] argue that benchmarks problematically jump from *domain* performances to conclusions about *general* AI capabilities. As Blili-Hamelin et al. [17] point out: “AI evaluation practices like benchmarking, as currently practiced, mostly treat individual

models as bearers of the properties they measure, and definers of AGI often propose tests that are mostly or entirely tests on individual agents“ [17, p. 146].

Another pivotal component in delineating AI pertains to functional characteristics. This approach primarily targets the capabilities that an AI must achieve in order to be classified as intelligent (e.g. [5, 30-32]). It is important to note that this cluster does not constitute an independent category but rather represents an instantiation of what *exactly* the machine would need to be able to perform, in order to outperform humans. As Dung [31] suggests, “[t]hese systems presumably need to be superior to humans in some strategically important domains (e.g., general planning, reasoning speed, persuasion, hacking, science etc.) and to have some notable degree of competence in many domains” [31, p. 138]. The specified functional domains that an AI must master (in order to be designated as such) are largely borrowed from engineering and information processing, as well as their respective categories and models. These include tasks such as command and control from cybernetics, brain modelling, cognitive science and other technical fields that engage with perception, memory, reasoning, learning, or language. Correspondingly, the scientific indicators, models and theorems in the examined literature draw upon the domain of technical apparatuses and their symbolic systems – such as formulae, modularity, lists, tables and actions – which are enacted as computation (see [60]). Moreover, as humans are taken up as the point of reference in the journey towards machine breakthroughs, this discourse does not hesitate to apply these technical analogies to humans – and in doing so, converting them into *machine-like entities*. This dynamic is also observable in robot-ethics, where machines become equated to humans as “quasi-others” [25 p. 75], and are discussed as moral recipients with rights [101]. Thus, we can note that this part of the literature reflects a functionalist and engineering-based understanding and applies it as a simile to both machines and humans, staging a competition between them.

Speculative AI out of control

A considerable proportion of the contributions examined invoke a definition of AI in the context of a loss of control, referring to the attainment of mental/cognitive states such as consciousness, awareness, sentience, autonomy, or moral sentiment (e.g., [5, 16, 30-32, 49, 53, 82, 93]). While the above depicted human-machine rivalry focused on *outcomes* in complexity games (which are operationalizable), these criteria often involve internal *states, processes* and *judgements* of the mind (thus phenomena which slip external manifestation).

Beltramini [16] “define[s] 'intelligent machine' in terms of sentient machines with general artificial intelligence ('AI')” [16, p. 258]. Harvey [49] stipulates that AI will develop motivations as it becomes aware of its “own mortality” [49, p. 49]. Saavedra-Rivano [82] follows this track, specifically pointing to evolutionary epochs:

“We look at the impact of AI in the short term and the longer term, the dividing point between these two periods being the moment when AI entities would acquire self-consciousness and be able to reason according to their own views of the world. There is of course plenty of discussion on whether that state of 'sentience' is possible at all for machines and also on when that would happen” [82, p. 319].

Even if machine *sentience* is not presented here as scientifically proven, it is nevertheless invoked as a distinguishing feature of epochs. However, these assumptions also serve as an indication of how highly speculative the discourse on AI beyond human controllability is in parts of the scientific literature. Another criterion brought to the fore is the achievement of autonomy, understood not only as machine *self-control* or *self-sufficiency*, but also as *self-awareness*. Arvan [60] reflects that human-like artificial moral agents would exhibit consciousness, intentionality as well as having a free will. In scenarios and conceptualizations that attribute the possibility of sentience and (self-)awareness to AIs, also an AI ‘patient ethic’ emerges as a proximate prospect. For example, Dung [30, p. 7] poses the question of “How to deal with risks of AI suffering?” – specifically addressing the potential suffering of AI, not the potential suffering of humans caused by AI (see also Beltramini [16]).

We note as a salient observation in the literature that when mental states related to consciousness, awareness and sentience are evoked, the reference point of the object under consideration quickly changes from AI to AGI and singularity - and with it authors enter a highly speculative realm. Instead of proving that AI *can* actually reach

mental states like consciousness, authors tend to postulate these circumstances simply as a given. Also, problematically, in the corpus AGI remains notoriously ill-defined. Observing how authors approach AGI in their papers, we suggest that it should rather be understood as a mindset than a founded theory. It is associated with the strong and assertive belief that AI will attain some mental states that make it equal to or surpass the human. Some papers show an almost messianic confidence towards this trajectory. Here the attainment of machine consciousness and sentience is frequently posited to be a matter of time or high likelihood, rather than of categorical possibility. This implied functionalist theory of mind [21] suggests that emergent internal phenomena such as consciousness will *appear* solely as a result of advancing algorithmic performance. However, other schools of thought in philosophy, psychology, neuroscience and biology have, for decades, challenged this assumption as implausible and speculative, depicting an ongoing, unresolved debate in the philosophy of mind [34, 50]. It remains unclear how phenomena of a different quality (e.g., consciousness) shall emerge by (simply) more of the same (algorithmic performance).

Algorithmic systems already are and will continue to *appear* increasingly intelligent and human, even if their imitation of traits such as humour, sadness or boredom does not extend to the *experience* of these emotions. However, the contributions within our sample that we discussed in this section advocate for functionalism as *machine consciousness*, treating AGI as an emergent process in the algorithmic entity – a realm which was before only reserved to humans, and partly, to animals.

Contested assumptions and the lack of benefit of an AI definition

A small number of the texts in the given corpus contend that the discourse surrounding the potential loss of AI control is highly speculative and controversial – and even without value. Johnson and Verdicchio [54] acknowledge the contradictory nature and high degree of speculation within certain positions across the discourse, stating: “The absence of any real understanding [...] gives futuristic thinkers a free hand to present misleading and sometimes contradictory scenarios” [54, p. 586] (see also [59] or [91]). A final, albeit small, part of the assessed literature distances itself from the benefits of a consolidated definition of AI and X-risks. Instead, these authors argue that the discourse should centre on the protected goods – such as human rights, safety, or human autonomy – that are potentially compromised by AI systems. The emphasis here is on the concrete potential for harm to individuals, irrespective of the complexity or the ‘intelligence’ of the algorithmic system in question. For instance, Bajgar & Horenovsky [7] present a focus on negative human rights, which would be “relatively agnostic to where we draw the line of what already counts as an AI system, and it could include present-day systems such as autonomous vehicles, robotic cleaners, or recommender systems” [7, p. 1048]. Negative human rights, as mentioned by Bajgar & Horenovsky [7] encompass the right to life, security of the person, the right to property, and the right not to be tortured. These rights are primarily discussed within the US legal sphere as rights of non-interference.

2) When will it happen? From the calculation of time and probability horizons to a sudden intelligence explosion

The considerable uncertainty surrounding the timing, and indeed the very possibility of the emergence of AI beyond human controllability, invites a broad spectrum of forecasts and speculations. How are time, probability and plausibility horizons conceptualised concerning the risks of an out-of-control AI (RQ II)? One tendency in the literature reviewed is to predict, or even calculate, probabilities and timeframes for the occurrence of events associated with AI X-Risks. This practice is often, as discussed above, linked to the emergence of AGI. The strand of literature treats the occurrence of future events as a calculable phenomenon that can be modelled and scientifically determined.

Speculative futures meet calculations of occurrences

Predictions about the time horizons for the development of AGI vary considerably among experts, to the extent that both their accuracy and their usefulness for guidance are questioned. Graham [42] highlights that while experts and researchers do not necessarily agree on an exact timeframe for the emergence of AGI, many bring

along their own estimations to the discussion. Several papers (a.o. [27, 72, 76, 97]) refer to the expert survey on human-level AI by Grace et al. [41], which found that experts, on average, predict a 50% probability of the attainment of human-level AI by 2061. Dung [32] “argue[s] for the conclusion that AI will lead to the permanent disempowerment (e.g. through extinction) of humanity by, at the latest, 2100.” Other authors within the literature corpus at least consider it a significant chance that AGI will be reached by the end of this century [40, 63, 84, 107].

Many papers link the attainment of X-risk AI with the coupling of risk assessment metrics and measurements, referring to notions of safety and controllability. Goldstein and Kirk-Giannini [40] propose a comprehensive risk assessment and speculate that the likelihood of a potential existential catastrophe resulting from misaligned AGI can be reduced to approximately 0.05% through the advancement of language agents (LLMs, e.g. ChatGPT). In their view, these agents can assist in resolving the “three important issues related to aligning AIs: reward misspecification, goal misgeneralization, and uninterpretability” [40, p. 1]. Yampolskiy [107] emphasises that the majority of advanced AI initiatives are devoid of integrated safety mechanisms, thereby underscoring the probability of the first AGI system being safe as being extremely low. This view is supported by Turchin [96], who proposes the establishment of a minimum acceptable level of AI risk as 5% of the “cumulative probability of powerful AI’s creation in a given time frame” [96, p. 47]. Moreover, Turchin [96] estimates that there is a 5% probability of AGI development within the next few years, coupled with the assumption that “human-level AI will pose an existential risk as soon as it will be created” [96, p. 47].

Such probability, threshold and occurrence calculations are very widespread in the literature and, as emphasised above, point to a peculiar reductionist worldview within the X-risk community. From this perspective, events and occurrences, no matter their complexity, can be formalized, calculated, modelled – and therefore controlled. We propose that these predictive practices can be understood as ‘technologies of distance’ [77] that have an important psychological effect. Numerical models and probabilistic estimates carry an aura of perceived objectivity and trustworthiness. In comparison to careful descriptive accounts that acknowledge their limitations or future-directed scenario building, which are subject to pathway interpretation and plausibility assessments, numerical calculations inhibit a sense of truth, precision and impartiality. They bestow authority to future tellers as “experts”, with their ability to predict, even calculate, the future. The use of metrics tied to future events is also performative for the entire AI future discourse: If a claim suggests that the definite occurrence x can be reduced by $y\%$ through measurement z , the consequence is an implicit imperative to take action.

The tendency to quantify risks and score probability of occurrences mobilizes a questionable ethical framework as a theoretical backdrop in parts of the discourse on AI X-risks, known as ‘longtermism’. Longtermism – not to be confused with long-term thinking – posits that the lives of all possible future human beings are more valuable than those currently living on earth, and in so doing, implies a moral obligation to maximise the total amount of ‘value’ in the universe and ensure our species does not fall short of its potential (see [95]). A key figure of reference in the corpus is the philosopher Nick Bostrom [19]. His conceptualization of AI X-risks is grounded in their potential impact on the advancement of ‘humanity’s potential’, including the moral value of all potential future generations of mankind. This highly speculative reasoning, which ties moral imperatives to a far future, is taken up by some authors. For example, in “Human Extinction and AI: What We Can Learn from the Ultimate Threat”, Lavazza and Vilaca [58] advocate for the creation of ‘heirs’ – “humanoid robots that reproduce our salient characteristics by imitation, thanks to AI powered by machine learning”. They assert that the potential extinction of *Homo sapiens* necessitates proactive measures: “It might be worth starting to contemplate a way to pass what is the best in the human species to what might be our ‘heirs’.” Attributing moral empathy to a speculative future is not met without opposition in the literature examined. In “The Problem with Longtermism”, Hyde [51] rejects longtermism outright, calling it “absurd” and dismissing its central premise – “the idea that we can even be morally concerned about what is a million years away, yet again obliged to do something about it” – as “utter folly” [51, p. 149]. This critique points to the absurdity of pitying a pain for entities that do not exist – except in stochastic models.

Also Thorstad [91] presents a well-argued rebuttal of the underlying assumptions supporting the calculation of the “AGI breakthrough”. He deconstructs models and theorems of accelerating growth, pointing to bottlenecks

and physical constraints that, from his point of view, most X-risk scholars simply fail to consider. He concludes with a call for scientific humility and robustness:

“The singularity hypothesis posits a sustained period of exponential or hyperbolic growth in the intelligence of artificial agents, continuing at least until machines exceed humans in intelligence by as much as humans exceed mice. These are extraordinary claims, and they should require correspondingly extraordinary evidence” [91, p. 4].

Sudden loss of control

Some scholars highlight the possibility of a sudden emergence or uncontrollable acceleration of developments leading to AI surpassing human controllability. Torres [93], for instance, discusses the risk of AGI emerging out of the blue and in an unpredictable manner: “AGI could be a momentary flash between sub-human-level AI and artificial superintelligence. An artificial superintelligence is a system that could significantly outperform every possible human in all cognitive domains” [93, p. 105]. Jilk [53] depicts a similar pathway: “In an intelligence explosion, initial creation of artificial intelligence with a critical mass of capabilities and drives is followed by an inexorable process of increases in that intelligence. [...] This process is usually viewed as uncontrolled, unstoppable, and accelerating” [53, p. 429]. Others question this run-away-dynamic. In their review of the X-risk literature, Armstrong and Sotala [5] stress the inherent uncertainty in predicting the development of advanced AI. Likewise, Yudkowsky [109] argues that pinpointing the emergence of AGI is nearly impossible. He suggests that clear evidence of AGI on the way may only become apparent within two years of its arrival ([109], see also [85]).

The sudden emergence of AGI is a narrative with psychological effects. Irrespective of intentionality, it paints a picture of looming threat, suggesting that humanity has merely a limited *kairos* window of action before reaching the point of no return. The notion of a disruptive, accelerationist technological development is frequently employed as a rhetorical device to symbolise an unpredictable and unprecedented moment in which a superintelligence bursts upon humanity and *invades* or *overthrows* it. However, the discourse is not clear concerning the indicators to look out for on the horizon regarding potentially threatening developments. Hanson & Yudkowsky [48], for example, argue that the development of advanced AI does not depend primarily on hardware availability, but on the emergence of an unprecedented seminal concept (i.e., unforeseeable genius momentum). The probability of such an occurrence, as posited by Turchin [96], is seen as heavily influenced by the number of researchers engaged in AI development. In this view the likelihood of such a pivotal conceptual leap is closely associated with the financial and attentional resources allocated to AI research at a given time. Psychologically powerful, this narrative necessitates a careful plausibility check regarding its economic, infrastructural and material prerequisites – which leads us to the last research question.

3) Unencumbered by socio-material constraints: On what is ignored

A firm declaration of an AI far-fetched future is ridden with prerequisites. AI does not develop in isolation but is embedded in the social and material, ranging from (geo-)political climate, economic investments, to the access to chips, training data and server farms. Given the aim of assessing the plausibility of proclaimed X-AI futures, these domains are pivotal because they carve out the very resource and infrastructure any AI development depends on. This leads us to ask: Which background conditions (material, institutional, economic) as well as societal circumstances are discussed in the futures towards out-of-control AI (RQ III)?

Here the picture among the assessed literature is striking. Almost no contribution in the corpus does justice to this perspective. Instead, AI development is approached as a stand-alone ‘autonomous’ agent, whose steady increase in capability is just depicted as a given, pointing to technological determinist worldview [104]. In the X-risk discourse, AI is sheltered inside a closed, formalized world which is imminently theory and model based. Being self-referential, it is seemingly unable to escape its own world of meaning.

Examining the literature, we note that the X-risk discourse seems predominantly popular in the natural sciences, lacking interdisciplinary papers that incorporate insights from the humanities and social sciences. This may be the

very reason for the dominance of functionalist and engineering parameters over social ones in the corpus. Recalling the notions of strategic ignorance and overshadowing from the introduction, it is revealing which aspects the X-risk discourse does *not* discuss in order to enable the postulation of catastrophic trajectories. The disregard for counterarguments, lessons learned from history, and insights from other scientific disciplines is very salient.

A few reflective exceptions exist. Within the literature corpus, Singler [87] provides a critical analysis of the prevailing narratives surrounding “AI apocalypticism”, contending that the (anticipated) advancements in AI “will, and do, also intermingle with our dreams of the future and affect our conceptions of ourselves now [...] depending on the narratives around them that are generated by both lay and expert audiences” [87, p. 174]. Singler’s note is similar to approaches in the social sciences which argue that AI should be considered situated and relational [60, 89-90], reworked and understood by different users and narratives, and enmeshed in constellations of power.

Thorstad [91] points to concrete bottlenecks and limitations regarding the resources and infrastructure AI depends on. He questions the accelerating growth of AI capabilities along the limits of producing ever smaller and denser transistors, which makes both their manufacture and interaction increasingly complex: “Any viable path to improving artificial intelligence will eventually bump up against resource constraints and the laws of physics in ways that are not easily overcome” [91, p. 10]. Moreover, our corpus includes a paper that explicitly addresses the strategic interests and power position of major technology companies within the domain and discourse of X-risks and related research. Leggett [59] adopts a critical power perspective and reflects on the societal preconditions of an out-of-control AI. By establishing an analogy between AI beyond human controllability and the capitalist economic system with its accelerating growth dynamics, he challenges conventional assumptions and offers a novel perspective on the matter:

“Superintelligence? In short, we have created a corporate market machine that is now capable of manipulating and controlling individual humans, and that is infinitely better, already, at this task than any human is, or could hope to be. And we have given this machine the single, overarching goal of obtaining a return to capital” [59, p. 736].

The commentary cautions against a debate that disregards the systemic risks for both individuals and society as a whole, pointing to the power wielded by a privileged group of affluent tech oligarchs, the ownership over AI infrastructure, as well as to the capitalist and sensational driven logics of media attention. In the overall picture, such critical voices represent the stark exception rather than the norm within the literature corpus examined. Unencumbered by the constraints of the socio-material realm, the X-risk debate predominantly operates within the speculative, often referring to bold predictions, questionable calculations, a functionalist theory of the mind, and an unwavering – at times, quasi-messianic – conviction in the AI singularity trajectory.

Concluding Discussion

In this paper, we interrogated the peer-reviewed corpus indexed in Scopus and Web of Science for the plausibility conditions of AI X-risks. We hypothesized that the stringent standards for academic indexing ensures that the included journals and articles are held to rigorous scrutiny, also concerning their quality of argumentation. The result reveals a multifaceted, and somewhat disconcerting picture.

A significant portion of authors privilege alarmist narratives that rest on anthropomorphic conceptualisations of AI and a functionalist theory of mind – some even attribute faculties such as ‘consciousness’, ‘autonomy’ and ‘sentience’ to computational systems. This framing not only imbues the scientific discourse with emotional, speculative expectations and in so doing, undermines its analytical value. Moreover, the navigation of these categories quickly comes along with a new background condition: a jump from assessing Artificial Intelligence to a much more speculative object of investigation, namely the attainment of Artificial General Intelligence – often used interchangeably with terms as singularity and superintelligence – and the accompanying risks of such

development. Both this jump and the related concepts, however, remain vaguely outlined and ill-defined within the corpus at hand.

Furthermore, authors often overlook the socio-technical foundations of AI, dedicating minimal attention to the necessary infrastructural and material preconditions of a supposedly accelerating AI. Unencumbered by socio-material constraints, AI is sheltered in a closed-up, formalized world which is imminently model based. This allows proclamations of vast futures with AI out of control, navigating in the purely speculative and theoretical. Notwithstanding this weak empirical socio-material reflection, it does not prevent many authors from predicting occurrences, AI breakthrough events and points-of no return with confidence and mathematical precision. In this epistemic worldview, complexity can be formalized, calculated, modelled – and therefore predicted and controlled. Our analysis indicates that a substantial part of the scientific discourse is not sufficiently critical of the underlying preconditions that need to be checked and covered to be able to assess, let alone proclaim, AI X-risk futures in the first place. We summarise the empirical results of our review in detail in Table 1 below, alongside respective questions to address the plausibility conditions invoked.

Table 1. Results and X-risk plausibility list

Research Question	Results of the Review	X-risk Plausibility Questions
Variable of comparison: How is AI defined? How is it linked to existential risk? (RQ I)	<p>Many papers in the X-risk community draw a human-machine analogy, displaying a tendency towards anthropomorphisation and a mechanistic worldview.</p> <p>AI in competition with humans – the goal is to surpass humans.</p> <p>Benchmarking as an indicator of AI performance with the problematic tendency of inductive generalization.</p> <p>AI defined via functional capabilities, implying an engineering understanding.</p> <p>Few papers: The value of defining AI is contested. Lack of benefit, rather focus on protected goods as negative human rights.</p>	<p>Are the progress and breakthroughs of AI justified by closed-world games, challenges, quests and benchmarks?</p> <p>How prevalent are anthropomorphic tendencies, such as equating human capabilities and understandings with those of machines?</p> <p>Which metaphors or symbolic references are used to describe the relationship between humans and machines?</p>
Speculative assumptions in relation to AI and (loss of) control (RQ I)	<p>A considerable proportion of the literature invokes speculative criteria such as consciousness, sentience or autonomy. High confidentiality that AI will attain these criteria, with AI developing into AGI/Superintelligence.</p> <p>AGI and its development paths are ill-defined.</p> <p>Advocation for functionalism as a theory of mind, treating AGI as an emergent process in the machine.</p> <p>Some papers suggest a moral patient ethic, ascribing ethical value to machines.</p>	<p>Are speculative criteria mobilised to define AI?</p> <p>Does the referent change from AI to AGI?</p> <p>Is AGI delineated as a point of reference? How, with what reference points?</p> <p>If so, by what criteria does AI develop into AGI?</p> <p>What is suggested as a proof that AGI is reached and that humanity loses controllability?</p> <p>Is AI's attainment of (super-)human properties seen as inevitable / an emergent result of a mere matter of more algorithmic power?</p>

<p>Indicators of development (RQ II)</p>	<p>Calculations of probability, thresholds and occurrences are very widespread in the AI X-risk community.</p> <p>Numerical models produce an aura of perceived objectivity, precision and truth. Bestows trust and changes the role from ‘authors’ to ‘experts.’</p> <p>The use of metrics evokes a sense of certainty and triggers a performative notion, calling for action.</p> <p>Some scholars proclaim the likelihood of a sudden loss of control (‘AGI flash’). Viewed as uncontrolled, unstoppable, and accelerating.</p> <p>The effect is again performative, suggesting a small window (<i>kairos</i>) to react.</p>	<p>Is the growth in AI capacities projected to be linear, exponential or contingent?</p> <p>Are X-risks presented as calculable events that can be modelled and scientifically determined through probability-, threshold- and occurrence-calculations?</p> <p>What is the tone of presentation, confidence, imagery used? Are rhetorical devices utilised to convey rupture, breakthrough, acceleration?</p>
<p>Sociopolitical and material embedding of X-risk future (RQ III)</p>	<p>Almost no contribution present. Instead, AI is portrayed as an ‘autonomous agent.’</p> <p>Predominant X-risk discourse lacks interdisciplinary approaches and insights. This results in an overshadowing of the social and material, liberating AI development from any real-world constraints.</p>	<p>Are the arguments surrounding X-risks embedded in economic, material and socio-political factors?</p> <p>Any questions of ownership, infrastructure or regulation raised?</p> <p>Is the development of AI argued as imminently theory/model based?</p>
<p>Who’s speaking? And for whom? (RQ III)</p>	<p>Mostly computer scientists and engineers. Philosophers like Nick Bostrom as prominent figures of reference, ‘Longtermism’ as a prominent school of thought.</p>	<p>Do the authors, and/or their organizations, have a distinct / (ill-)legitimate interest (personal, financial, political), in drawing attention to AI development?</p>

To conclude: The perception that AI development is accelerating beyond human controllability has fuelled a proliferation of narratives that utilizes bold hypotheses and strong doomsday rhetorics – even in indexed, peer-reviewed journals.

This also points to a limitation of this study. Retrieving scientific literature from impactful scientific databases such as Scopus and Web of Science covers substantial peer-reviewed literature – but it does not cover all publications in the field. This means that the given corpus of literature does not encompass the scientific contributions published in smaller and/or less established scientific journals. However, exactly because the proclamation of the AI X-risk discourse being so contested in public and fuelled by non-academic venues, we expected some orientation and clarity from the peer-reviewed literature, given the stringent standards for indexing in Scopus and Web of Science. We hypothesized that the included journals and articles are held to rigorous academic scrutiny, also concerning their plausibility of argumentation, rendering them well-suited for a critical, plausibility-focused review of AI X-risks futures. The results do not confirm this hypothesis.

Returning to the introduction, the proclaimed AI X-risk futures can rather be labelled as speculative “wishful-worries” [20], than plausible trajectories that policymakers must take into account. But this comes along with a worrying side-effect. It is crucial to clarify that we do not dismiss the possibility that the further development of AI entails substantial, even detrimental, societal risks. Quite the contrary: our concern lies with the way these AI

risks are currently framed and discussed in the public arena – and, as we argue with this paper, also in much of the scientific literature. Rather than cantering the discourse on anticipating the most extreme and catastrophic outcomes of AI – and devoting primary attention to preventing these hypothetical scenarios – we advocate for a de-escalation of rhetoric and a shift in focus in the here and now. This is why we suggest, deduced from the undertaken results of this work, an AI X-risk plausibility list (table 1). The questions aim at deconstructing and identifying problematic AI X-risk conceptualizations and doomsday narratives. Herewith we hope to offer a heuristic toolkit for analysts, policy makers and academics to substantiate a speculative, emotionally loaded, and overhyped debate about AI futures.

In the context of these plausibility questions, we specifically suggest concentrating on the structural and socio-technical characteristics of AI systems that are the prerequisites for any AI futures to emerge. It is imperative to critically examine what it means to delegate increasing levels of societal control to machines we neither fully comprehend in their calculation processes and decisions outputs. The same counts for the political loss of control over AI, pointing to the salient issue of the prevailing power structure of major technology companies in model development, maintenance, auditing [99] - and their dominant speech position in public. This development towards centralisation and provider dependency is a significant cause of lock-in effects and manifests the current power position of tech oligarchs in the Silicon Valley – and therefore the sensationalist rhetoric of doomsday AI.

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